

Experiment In Distance Education Based On 3d Virtual Learning Environment

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Abstract:

The 3D virtual learning environment based on Web3D technologies has strong interactivity and immersive, provides a new means to improve the quality of the virtual experiment in distance education. In this paper, on the basis of discussing the characteristics and the distinctive advantages of the 3D virtual learning environment in distance education, a virtual experiment is designed and implemented in Open Simulator preliminary verify the validity of applying the 3D virtual learning environment to the virtual experiment in distance education.

Keywords- *3D virtual learning environment; virtual learning environment; virtual experiment; distance education; open simulator.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the era of Web 2.0, the continuous development of information technology has brought about great and profound changes in the way that people learn, it also announces the arrival of e-Learning 2.0 [1]. At the same time, distance education has made great progress under the impetus of Web 2.0 technologies represented by Twitter, RSS and Wiki, the emergence of MOOCs (Massive open online courses) is the most typical case. On the one hand, MOOCs have gotten a lot of attention in distance education, because it has been realizing the global sharing of high quality education resources and making large-scale personalized learning possible, but on the other hand, the distance education represented by MOOCs still cannot obviously improve the effect of the virtual experiment in distance education. The virtual experiments that are displayed in a two-dimensional form, such as Flash, fail to give the learners a strong sense of social presence and a realistic experience to environment. They also cannot support the learners' collaborative learning during the process of the virtual experiments. In order to improve the current situation of the virtual experiment in distance education, this paper tries to introduce the 3D virtual learning environment (3D VLE) based on Web3D technologies to distance education, so that it's strong interactivity and immersive can be used to improve the effect and quality of the virtual experiment in distance education.

This paper discusses the characteristics and the distinctive advantages of the 3D virtual learning environment based on Web3D technologies in distance education. Then a virtual experiment is designed and implemented in Open Simulator to preliminary verify the validity of the virtual experiment in the 3D virtual learning environment.

2. THE DEFINITION OF THE VIRTUAL EXPERIMENT IN DISTANCE EDUCATION

The concrete definition of virtual experiment is generally dependent on actual researches. In some studies, the virtual experiment is a virtual environment that is realized in computer system by virtual reality techniques, in which the experimenters can complete all scheduled experiments like in real life

environment [2]. In this paper, the virtual experiment in distance education means that the learners can carry out a variety of experiments in the virtual experiment environment through their digital devices, the virtual experiment environment can be two-dimensional or three dimensional and it has a certain similarity to the one in real life.

3. THE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE 3D VLE

“3D virtual learning environment” is often referred to as “Immersive virtual learning environment” or “3D virtual worlds”. It usually refers to a kind of the virtual learning environment based on Web3D technologies. Experts have different opinions about the definition of “virtual learning environment”, the author agrees with Oren A’s viewpoint that “Virtual Learning Environment” is a complete learning environment, which includes learning resources, teaching strategies and relevant support tools [3]. The 3D virtual learning environment based on Web3D technologies has the following characteristics.

A. Interactivity

The built-in tools of the 3D virtual learning environment can support the synchronous and asynchronous interaction between the learners. Furthermore, the real-time interaction between the learners and the virtual things is also supported.

B. Sociality

The 3D virtual learning environment can create a realistic social atmosphere for the learners by supporting their real-time online status and putting them into the same virtual scene at the same time.

C. Creativity

The 3D virtual learning environment adheres to the principle of “User Generated Content (UGC)”. It encourages the learners to create various virtual things independently by using the built-in 3D modelling tools and programming languages.

D. Openness

The learners only need a client and an account to log in the 3D virtual learning environment. Then they will get their own avatar and start to do free activities. In addition, the 3D virtual learning environment has realized resources opening and sharing by integrating network resources.

E. Immersive

The 3D virtual learning environment can bring a strong sense of immersion to the learners, so that their interest in learning can be inspired better.

4. THE DISTINCTIVE ADVANTAGES OF THE 3D VLE IN DISTANCE EDUCATION

A. Largely shortening the transactional distance

In distance education, Moore’s theory of transactional distance regards the distance between the learners and instructors as a psychological and communications gap, not just a simple physical distance [4]. The transactional distance largely depends on how many dialogues that happens between the instructors and the learners. The dialogue can be understood as a kind of effective means of communication between the learners and instructors in distance education. To put it another way, in the process of distance education, the more dialogues happens between the instructors and the learners, the smaller the transactional distance will become.

There are many different types of built-in communication media can be used to support the dialogue in the 3D virtual learning environment, including Instant Messenger, Voice Chat, Avatar's body language, etc. It is worth noting that some Web 2.0 applications can also be integrated into the 3D virtual learning environment, such as Twitter and Blog. Unlike the split experience of the dialogue in the other modes of distance education, such as MOOCs, the learners in the 3D virtual learning environment can carry out dialogue with the teachers or other learners through a variety of forms completely on the premise of not leaving the current virtual learning scene, so the transactional distance can be largely shortened and the learners' learning experience can be improved in the 3D virtual learning environment.

B. Better supporting constructivism learning theory

Constructivism learning theory emphasizes the learner entered teaching and advocates by situation creating and collaborative learning to support learners' meaning construction [5]. It attaches great importance to the learners' initiative and pioneering spirit in the learning process. In addition, the instructors should provide the learners with a number of opportunities to apply what they learned in different situations.

Apparently, the immersive and the sociality of the 3D virtual learning environment are very supportive of constructivism learning theory. In the vivid 3D virtual learning environment, for the instructors, they are no longer playing the role of a knowledge instiller, but the role of an organizer, helper, and facilitator to use the variety of the technical means to help the learners. For the learners, with the help of the instructors, they mainly through the interaction with the virtual things to acquire knowledge, and the knowledge they learned will be internalized rapidly while they collaborate with one another.

C. Effectively overcoming learners' psychological barriers

Each of the learners and instructors has an avatar in the 3D virtual learning environment and they can personalize the image of their own avatars. Represented by the avatars, without face to face, the learners can use the built-in communication tools to have dialogue with the instructors or the other learners. Obviously, this way of communication is more likely to let the learners feel comfortable than the way in traditional video remote teaching, it is also more likely to let the learners feel more natural and more realistic than the way based on the text in 2D virtual learning environment, such as Blackboard or Moodle. Most importantly, with the aids of the avatars' individual learners' psychological barriers could be overcome easily. For example, in the other modes of distance education, individual learners may be reluctant to communicate directly with the instructors or the other learners, just because of their introverted personality.

D. Characteristically implementing subject teaching

Compared with the other modes of distance education, especially MOOCs, the unique creativity and interactivity of the 3D virtual learning environment make it possible to implement distinctive subject teaching, in that case, the learners can get a more meaningful learning experience. Take physical experiment course for example, by using the built-in 3D modelling tools and programming languages, the instructors can realize the realistic simulation of various physical phenomena, such as gravity and free-fall, then the learners can get the correct understanding of the knowledge according to the instant feedback from the virtual experiment.

5. THE VALIDITY OF THE VIRTUAL EXPERIMENT IN 3D VLE

In order to preliminary verify the validity of applying the 3D virtual learning environment to the virtual experiment in distance education, the author designs and implements an inquiry-based virtual experiment in Open Simulator for the electrical experiment course of junior middle school. In this

study, aiming at the deficiencies of the teaching of the electrical experiment course in junior middle school, the author tries to improve them through the virtual experiment in the 3D virtual learning environment. The following are the main content of this study.

A. *The platform structures*

There are many popular technology platforms used to build the 3D virtual learning environment, including Second Life, Open Simulator, Virtual Reality Platform (VRP), etc. Open Simulator, as the open source and free version of Second Life, fully inherited the various features of Second Life. Because it can be easily localized and extended, Open Simulator has broad prospects for the development in distance education. For the above reasons, in this study, the 3D virtual learning environment is built based on the Open Simulator platform.

B. *The current situation analysis*

In this section, four factors about the electrical experiment course of junior middle school are surveyed by questionnaire, including the present situation of the course, course quality, students' interest level and degree of participation. In the 205 questionnaires distributed, 194 valid questionnaires are collected. Analysis shows that the students who rarely have the opportunities to do experiments on their own account for about 88 per cent of all the students, all they can do is only to watch the teachers making experiments in the process of classroom teaching. The main causes of this phenomenon are the neglect of this course and the lack of the experimental equipment[6].

C. *The model of the virtual experiment*

In this section, the model of the inquiry-based virtual experiment is proposed on the basis of combining the characteristics of inquiry learning and the 3D virtual learning environment, as shown in Fig. 1. This model embodies the main idea of the learner-centered of Constructivism Learning Theory. It can be seen that the 3D virtual learning environment based on Open Simulator provides four aspects of support for the inquiry-based virtual experiment, including the situations support, evaluation support, tools support, resources support. Moreover, to promote the students' meaning construction, the teachers are playing the role of an inspirer, helper, observer, listener, valuator and guider in the whole process of the inquiry-based virtual experiment, instead of a knowledge instiller.

Figure 1. The model of the virtual experiment

D. The instructional design of the virtual experiment

In this section, the author carries out the instructional design of the inquiry-based virtual experiment for the electrical experiment course of junior middle school, including analysis of the teaching objectives, analysis of the teaching content, analysis of the difficult points, analysis of the learners, and the design of teaching process. Fig. 2 shows the teaching process in the virtual experiment.

Figure 2. The teaching process in the virtual experiment.

Take a virtual experiment activity process for example. According to the teaching process, firstly, the students in the virtual experiment environment will be inspired by the vivid virtual scenes or the teachers to produce a question. For instance, “what is the distinguishing feature of the current size in a series circuit?” Secondly, the students will think or discuss about that question, then put forward a preliminary idea. For instance, “the current size in a series circuit may equal everywhere”. Thirdly, on the basis of the preliminary idea, the students will move forward to come up with the exploring solution, so that the correctness of the preliminary idea can be validated in the next step. For example, “a solution is to test the three current sizes of three different positions in a series circuit and then compare the three current sizes to check the correctness of the preliminary idea”. Fourthly, the students will follow their exploring solution to do the experiment. If the experiment turns out that the preliminary idea is right, then the students will enter into the next two steps to draw a conclusion and do self-reflection, otherwise, the students will go back to the previous steps to correct themselves, until they succeed.

E. The realization of the inquiry-based virtual lab

In this section, according to the model of the inquiry based virtual experiment and the experiment content, the inquiry-based virtual lab is developed and implemented mainly by the built-in 3D modelling tools and linden scripting language (LSL) as well as other related software, such as Blender and 3D MAX. The main content of this section that need to be realized include the virtual experiment scenes, experiment resources, learning tools, and evaluation tools, as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. The experiment equipment in the inquiry-based virtual lab.

F. The trial of the virtual experiment

For validating the validity of the virtual experiment in the 3D virtual learning environment, a group of junior middle school students of grade three are selected as the subjects to make the virtual experiment, as shown in Fig. 4. In the specified test period, such as two months, the subjects can log into the 3D virtual learning environment at any time and any place to do the virtual experiment according to the instructional design.

Figure 4. The trail of the virtual environment

At the end of the trial period, the subjects are interviewed to collect the feedback information about the virtual experiment.

most all of the subjects can run it smoothly on their personal computers and get a good experience, benefit from the continuous improvement of network bandwidth and hardware configuration. But because there are some technical cognitive difficulties in the Open Simulator platform for the subjects, such as the various operations of avatar, most of the subjects were at a loss when they first logged in the 3D virtual learning environment, even though their curiosity was deeply attracted. In fact, some relevant introduction materials had been provided in advance to the subjects to reduce the time that they need to get familiar with the environment, but the effect is not very ideal. This problem deserves further study in future work[7].

Then, about the virtual experiment, the interview results show generally that the subjects are willing to put it as a way of distance learning in their spare time, because they feel the simulation in the virtual experiment is realistic, they can easily immerse into the 3D virtual learning environment as long as they are no longer at a loss, and their learning motivation can be stimulated better. Moreover, the subjects also suggest that the interactivity of the virtual equipment in the virtual lab should be further enriched, so they can get a better learning effect and experience.

CONCLUSION

The 3D virtual learning environment provides a new means to improve the effect and quality of the virtual experiment in distance education. In the paper, the characteristics and the distinctive advantages of the 3D virtual learning environment in distance education are discussed. Then a virtual experiment is designed and implemented in Open Simulator to preliminary verify the validity of the virtual experiment in the 3D virtual learning environment.

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